

Designation	Tillers (av no./hill)	Panicles (%)	Silver shoots (%)	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Late</i>				
IET56-56	18.1	40.2	52.8	4.9
Suku Gurmatiya ^a	9.0	26.7	52.8	1.6
Safari 17 ^a	4.3	39.2	31.3	0.9
Mahsuri	23.8	22.3	25.2	3.7
<i>Resistant</i>				
Bangoli 2 (GMR 11)	9.8	94.9	0.1	6.1
Bangoli 3 (GMR 17)	15.8	91.1	0.0	5.0
Bangoli 5 (GMR18)	10.3	87.2	0.6	6.3
RP9-4	10.8	84.9	0.0	6.2
Bangoli 6 (GMR19)	12.0	82.8	0.2	6.3
RPW6-17	10.0	87.0	0.1	5.4
R2384	6.8	71.6	0.0	5.2
R35-2750	8.8	76.1	0.4	6.8
R35-2752	7.4	49.8	0.4	5.6

^aBroadcast.

Tillers, silver shoots, and panicles

Performance of rices of various maturity groups in relation to gall midge.

(see table). Transplanted paddy always yielded more than broadcast paddy.

In the medium maturity group, silver shoots ranged from 6.2 to 45.6%.

Gall midge was severe in both tall and semidwarf varieties of the late maturity group.

Resistant varieties not only withstood the gall midge attacks but also performed well in panicle formation and yield.

The performance of each paddy group was determined. The average percentage of panicles decreased gradually from early to late maturity groups, but was highest in the resistant varieties (see figure). Similarly, the percentage of gall midge infestation, as indicated by silver shoots, was lower in the early group and higher in the medium and late groups. Medium-maturing varieties yielded highest. Resistant varieties performed best.

Large-scale cultivation of resistant varieties can help control gall midge and reduce the use of insecticides, which not only are costly but also perform poorly against gall midge. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought resistance

C22, a promising rice culture for semidry tracts

P. Vivekanandan, R. Balasubramanian, A. Thyagarajan, S. Sivaraman, and M. Ramachandran, Paddy Experiment Station, Tirur — 602025, Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu, India

The variety C22 was evolved at the University of the Philippines at Los Baños from the cross Tjere Mas/BPI-76//Palawan/Azucena. It was received through the International Rice Testing

Program, coordinated by IRRI, as one of the entries in the Third International Upland Rice Yield Nursery.

A medium-tall variety with long slender grain, C22 matures in 135 days.

It was tested in yield evaluation trials for 3 consecutive years in samba season (Aug–Dec 1976–78). The popular varieties IR20 and TKM8 were also tested in the trials (see table). ■

Performance of C22 at Tirurkuppam, Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Mean yield (t/ha)	Increase over TKM8 (%)	1000-grain wt (g)	Grain shape
C22	3.7	49.1	22.4	Slender
IR20	2.8	12.8	20.5	Medium
TKM8	2.5	—	19.7	Medium